

DEVELOPING ENHANCED FILTERING MECHANISM TO DETECT SPOOFED MAIL

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ABSTRACT

Spam emails is a major issue on today's Internet, resulting in financial losses for businesses and annoyance for individual users. Email spoofing is a type of cyber attack in which a hacker sends an email that has been manipulated to appear to have come from a trusted source. The attacker creates a spam email attached with minor corrections in the trusted mail, which aims to bypassing the anti-spam deduction in GMAIL. Using this filtering mechanism help to filter the receive mail to identify that mail is harm full or not. It help to prevent in email phishing attack. In this paper, find the IP-ADDRESS of the domain, Then identify the exact server name of the received MAIL-ID.

INTRODUCTION

Phishing is a type of online scam in which criminals pose as legitimate organisations through email, text message, advertisement, or other means in order to steal sensitive information. This is usually accomplished by including a link that appears to take you to the company's website to fill out your information - but the website is a clever forgery, and the information you provide goes directly to the scammers. Email phishing, also known as "deception phishing," is one of the most well-known attack types. Malicious actors send emails to users impersonating a well-known brand, then use social engineering tactics to create a false sense of urgency, leading them to click on a link or download an asset.

Usually, the links lead to unsafe websites where users' devices are infected with malware or passwords are stolen when the user opens the document, the malware is installed.

How to Identify the phishing email:

The majority of people are aware of some of the key indicators of a phishing email. However, some traditional things to look for when attempting to mitigate risk include

- **Legitimate information:** Look for contact information or other legitimate information about the spoofed organisation, then look for things like misspellings or a sender email address with the incorrect domain.
- **Malicious and benign code:** Be wary of anything that attempts to fool Exchange Online Protection (EOP), such as downloads or links with misspellings.
- **Shortened links:** Avoid clicking on any shortened links because they are used to trick Secure Email Gateways.
- **Fake brand logo:** Check the message for any logos that appear real, as they may contain malicious HTML attributes.
- **Little text:** Ignore emails with just an image and very little text because the image could contain malicious code.

A Methods for classifying phishing emails:

The phishing email filter is Carried out by the process of classifying new messages. It can examine messages to classify them either separately by checking the email for the presence of specific words, as in keyword filtering, or through a learning-based filter that analyses a collection of labelled training data, and so on. An email message is divided into two parts: the header and the body. Email headers include a structured set of fields such as From, To, Subject, and so on. The body of an email is always preceded by header lines that identify the message's specific routing information, such as the sender, recipient, date, and subject. The email body

is the part that we always see because it contains the actual content of the message. The email message structure taxonomy is presented in. Along with an illustration of the basis for feature selection and extraction.

What is mail server?

A mail server, also known as, a mail transport agent (MTA), a mail router, or an internet mailer, is a software that receives incoming email from local users and remote senders and forwards outgoing messages for delivery. A mail server is a computer that is dedicated to run these applications. Mail server programmes such as Microsoft Exchange, Exim, and Sendmail are common examples.

A mail server collaborates with other programmes to create a messaging system. A messaging system includes all of the applications required to keep email running smoothly. When you send an email, a programme like Microsoft Outlook forwards it to a mail server. The mail server then forwards the message to another mail server or to a holding area on the same server to be forwarded later.

Types of mail server?

Mail servers are classified into two types: incoming mail servers and outgoing mail servers.

An incoming mail server receives and delivers email to a user's inbox. The two main types of incoming mail servers are Post Office Protocol 3 (POP3) and Internet Message Access Protocol (IMAP).

POP3, for example, downloads email from a server and stores incoming email messages on a single device until the user opens the email client. Once the user downloads the email, it is automatically deleted from the server, unless the "keep mail on server" setting is enabled. Many internet service providers offer their users POP3 email accounts, as they are more space efficient.

IMAP servers allow users to preview, delete, and organise emails previous to transferring them from the email server to multiple devices. Emails are copied and stored on the server until the user deletes them.

An outgoing mail server communicates with a user's machine via the Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP), which handles the email delivery process. To send emails from email clients, SMTP servers collaborate with other mail servers, such as POP3 or IMAP.

ANALYSIS OF AN EMAIL

The header of an email message is examined during analysis. The email header serves as the mail's envelope. Every email received is associated with an email header. The main method of email-related attacks and identification is the analysis of the email header. Each email contains only one header. RFCs have defined the following terms:

- **From:** Contains the sender's email address.
- **To:** Contains the recipient's email address.
- **Subject:** Contains information about the message's topic.
- **Date:** Contains the time and date when the mail was sent.
- **Reply-To:** Contains the email address that the recipient will use to respond.
- **Message-ID:** This is an automatically generated field that uniquely identifies the message.

Received: Information about mail servers involved in message transmission that can be used to trace the path of message transmission. The Received and Message-ID fields are particularly important for determining the integrity and authenticity. The received field is the most important and usually the most reliable field in the email header because it is automatically added by email servers during email transmission from the sender to the receiver. This calculates information about all the servers or computers. If the sender's machine's local time was incorrectly set, the time difference calculation between intermediate mail servers helps to determine the actual time the mail was sent. If their differences exceed this threshold, there is a chance that the email.

Email Filtering Techniques:

- **Reputation-Based Email Filters:** Attempts to prevent spam or allow legitimate email by filtering out known spammers or approving trusted senders using reputation databases. RBLs are lists of domains, URLs, and IP addresses that have been examined and determined to be potential security threats. RBLs are one of the most common ways for businesses to use spam filtering to protect themselves.
- **Safelisting:** Allows organizations to specify which senders' emails they accept by adding them to a list.

- **Blocklisting:** Allows organizations to choose which senders to block email from by adding them to a list.
- **Temporary blocklisting also known as greylisting :** Enables an organization to combat spam by temporarily rejecting any email from a sender it does not identify. If the message is genuine, the sending server will try again after a short delay, and the email will be accepted.
- **Anti-virus:** Uses signature-based and non-signature-based technology to protect against new and existing viruses, as well as other forms of malicious code.
- **Content Analysis:** Allows you to block emails based on the content of the message. For instance, if a message contains specific words, the content filter can determine that it is spam. Another example is if the message included an attachment and the organisation does not want it to be delivered. Bayesian analysis is another type of content filtering. By learning from each message it scans, Bayesian analysis improves spam filtering. The greater the number of messages scanned the more effective the analysis.

EMAIL FILTERING MECHANISM

Email filtering software is a type of security tool that inspects both inbound and outbound email traffic. These tools scan emails for security risks such as spam, malware, and potentially suspicious links or attachments before they reach the end user's mailbox or leave the end user's server. This prevents messages that have been identified as potentially posing security risks from reaching their intended recipients. Whether the potential security risk was intentionally or unintentionally passed along, this software helps ensure that each end user's outgoing messages adhere to organizational policy.

Accurate and customizable anti-spam filters

When overly aggressive filtering software flags legitimate emails as spam, it's critical to look for a solution that uses near real-time pattern recognition, intellectual capacity, and machine learning to detect threats and reduce false positives.

Fig 1: FILTERING PROCESS

Email filtering software importance:

Having a reliable email filtering software solution in place is crucial because emails are one of the most popular attack channels for hackers.

Malware is not all the same. Some can be an annoyance rather than a serious threat. However, some extremely damaging varieties can steal or edit sensitive data, wipe entire hard drives, or take control of the host server's operations, allowing the hacker to monitor all email traffic and thus expose the entire company to potential threat. Some hackers are also skilled impersonators, posing as trustworthy or reputable figures in order to obtain information from a company employee. Because of the variety of potential threats, detailed and dedicated email filtering software is a must for any MSP hoping to protect their customers from attack.

EXPLANATION:

In this project, I did my filtering mechanism to determine whether the received mail is spam or not. It helps organizations in preventing phishing attacks. The majority of phishing attacks take place via email and messages.

If the attacker sends email to the victim, this mechanism uses rules and policies to filter the email before it reaches the mail server. If more than 15 possibilities occur, the mail is quarantined, and this mechanism retrieves information about it, such as the legitimate mail header, time spoofed mail header, DNS lookup, domain name, mail server, IP address, and so on. If the number of trustable possibilities is less than 15, mail will be sent to the mail server. Nowadays, organizations face spam mail problems on a daily basis.

ALGORITHM FOR DETECTING FORGED EMAILS:

Step 1: Read the message header from bottom to top line.

Step 2: Identify the various header fields to detect spoofing.

Step 3: Examine the Date: and Received: fields to determine Timestamps should be converted to UTC.

Step 4: Contrast these timestamps with the norm. A timestamp is required foremail communication.

Step 5: Use the IP address to perform a DNS or reverse DNS lookup. Available addresses and domain names in the Received: fields. .

Step 6: Cross-check the domain name in the Message-ID field. with the domain name added by in the Received: field the sender's mail server.

Step 7: Check the Received: field for mail servers that match.

Step 8: If more than two methods show an imbalance, the email is likely spoofed.

CREATE A OWN MAIL SERVER:

SOURCES INSTALLED:

- 1.INSTALLED/CONFIGURE WEBMAIL/DOVECOT MAIL SERVER
2. INSTALLED EPEL-REPOSITORY
3. INSTALLED POSTFIX
4. INSTALLED SQUIRREL-MAIL

INSTALLED EPEL-REPOSITORY:

The EPEL repository is an additional package repository that provides quick access to commonly used software installation packages. Fedora contributors wanted to use Fedora packages they maintain on RHEL and other compatible distributions, so this repo was created. Simply put, the goal of this repository was to improve access to software on Enterprise Linux compatible distributions.

INSTALLED POSTFIX:

Postfix is a well-known Mail Transfer Agent (MTA) that is used to determine routes and send emails. This cross-platform server is open-source, free, and can be installed on most UNIX-like operating systems. Postfix is made up of numerous client and server.

programs: the latter usually runs in the background, while the former is used by user or administrator programs. Postfix's structure is modular: it is made up of several small, self-contained executables. There are also various parameters, features, and options available. Another important aspect of Postfix is that it was designed to address the shortcomings of Sendmail. A strong configuration protects Postfix user data from leakage, abuse, and spam.

INSTALLED SQUIRRELMAIL:

Squirrel Mail is a design that tries to offer an IMAP proxy server as well as a WEB-BASED EMAIL CLIENT. Squirrel Mail is compatible with any other operating system that supports PHP and can be used in collaboration with a LAMP stack. To transmit emails, the web server needs a connection to both an SMTP server and the IMAP server containing the email. SquirrelMail was added to the server when webmail was first made available to server users more than a year back. Its appearance and feature set haven't changed much since its introduction. PHP-based webmail software called SquirrelMail follows industry standards. IMAP and SMTP protocol support is built-in pure PHP support, and all pages render in pure HTML 4.0 (without the need for JavaScript) for optimal browser compatibility.

Fig 2: SQUIRREL-MAIL LOGIN PAGE

Fig 3: MAIL INBOX

SPAM FILTERING MECHANISM:

MACHINE LEARNING MODEL USING NAIVE BAYES ALGORITHM:

- Data cleaning
- EDA
- Text Preprocessing
- Model building
- Deployed in stream-lit
- Website

DATA CLEANING:

Data cleaning is the process of locating and eliminating or rectifying false, insufficient, or unnecessary data from a dataset. Data cleaning is a crucial stage in machine learning since the calibre of the data used to train a model can greatly affect its performance and accuracy.

Naive Bayes is a well-liked classification method that determines the likelihood of a specific result given a set of features. Because it can classify emails as spam or not rapidly based on their content, it is frequently employed in spam prediction.

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA):

- The purpose of exploratory data analysis (EDA) is to get a knowledge of the dataset, find patterns, trends, and anomalies, and prepare the data for modelling. EDA is commonly carried out by visualising and summarising data using statistical approaches.
- To perform EDA with Naive Bayes for spam prediction, we first need to gather and preprocess the data. This may include tasks such as cleaning the text, removing stop words, and converting the text into numerical features using techniques such as Bag-of-Words or Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF).

•Once the data is prepared, we can begin with EDA by exploring the distribution of the features in the dataset. For example, we might plot the distribution of the frequency of each word in the spam and non-spam messages. This can give us an idea of the features that are most informative for classification.

•Throughout the EDA process, it is critical to remember the limits of Naive Bayes and the assumptions it makes about the data. When there are dependencies between features or when the dataset is skewed, Naive Bayes may not perform effectively.

DATA PREPROCESSING:

Data preprocessing is an important stage in machine learning that involves cleaning and transforming raw data into an analysis-ready state. Here are some common data preparation techniques:

•**Tokenization:** is the process of separating text into separate words or tokens. Tokenization is vital for text analysis since it allows us to count the frequency of particular terms and develop models on that basis.

•**Removing special characters:** entails removing any characters that are not letters or numbers, such as punctuation marks or special symbols. This procedure can aid with the simplification of the data and the removal of any noise that may interfere with the analysis.

•**Remove stop words and punctuation:** Stop words are common words that have little significance, such as "the," "and," or "a." Removing them can help to reduce data noise and focus on more relevant words.

•**Stemming:** the process of reducing words to their base form, or stem. This can help to group related words together and decrease the data's complexity. For example, "jump", "jumped", and "jumping" would all be stemmed to "jump".

The Naive Bayes algorithm is a prominent machine learning technique for classification applications. It operates by assessing the likelihood of a specific input belonging to each class and then selecting the class with the highest probability as the output.

MODEL BUILDING:

In machine learning, **model building** refers to the process of training a predictive algorithm or model with a dataset to make predictions or choices about fresh, unknown data.

•**Spam prediction** is one of the most common applications of Naive Bayes. In this case, the algorithm is trained on a dataset of emails, each of which is labelled as spam or not spam (ham). The algorithm learns the relationship between the words and phrases in the emails and their accompanying labels, and then utilises that information to predict whether or not a new email is spam.

- The training procedure is estimating the possibility of each word or phrase appearing in a spam or ham email and then using these probabilities to develop a model that can predict whether or not an email is spam. When a new email is received, the algorithm calculates the probability of it being spam or not based on the words and phrases it contains, and classifies it accordingly.

WEBSITE- STREAM-LIT:

Streamlit is an open-source Python framework used for building web applications. It provides an easy-to-use interface for data scientists and machine learning engineers to create interactive dashboards and visualizations.

To deploy a machine learning model using Streamlit, one can follow the following steps:

- Train a machine learning model on a dataset
- Save the trained model
- Write a Streamlit application to load the saved model and make predictions
- Deploy the Streamlit application on a web server or a cloud platform

Now, let's use the example of spam prediction using Naive Bayes to explain how Streamlit can be used to deploy a machine learning model. Once the model is trained, we can save it using a Python library such as joblib or pickle. Then, we can write a Streamlit application that loads the saved model and accepts user input in the form of an email message. The application will then use the loaded model to predict whether the input email is spam or not.

STREAM-LIT WEB APPLICATION:

Fig 4: SPAM PREDICTION WEB INTERFACE

Fig 5: SPAM PROVED

Fig 6: NOT A SPAM PROVED

SUMMARIES AND DISCUSSIONS:

The purpose of this paper is to provide a comprehensive overview of phishing email attacks and their solutions. Current security measures are ineffective at preventing phishing attacks, particularly zero-day attacks. The following are summaries and comments on the various protection measures investigated in the literature survey.

- **Network-level security:** It must be updated on a regular basis based on domain and IP address blacklisting. Because it is reactive in nature, it can only be updated after a pattern of abuse has been observed for some time.

- **Authentication techniques work** on two levels. As evidenced by increasingly successful phishing attacks, user level authentication using a password as credentials can simply be broken. Domain-level authentication provided by both the sender and the recipient is a method of obtaining confidential information via fraudulent emails that appear to be legitimate. We have provided a survey of the defences against these phishing email attacks. This survey contributes to a better understanding of the phishing email problem, the current solution space, and the future scope of phishing email filtering. Approaches described in the literature still have significant limitations in terms of accuracy and performance, particularly when dealing with zero-

day phishing email attacks. Most phishing email classifiers are based on supervised learning, which requires them to learn before they can be used to detect a new attack; unsupervised learning, which is faster but has a low level of accuracy; or hybrid (supervised and unsupervised) learning, which is time-consuming and expensive.

CONCLUSION:

Email spoofing is a growing security risk that necessitates sophisticated countermeasures to protect email users from its disastrous consequences. However, the majority of well-established anti-spoofing techniques are server-oriented and thus do not give users explicit control over spoof attacks. A client-oriented anti-spoofing application was proposed, but it could only be used on a single subnet. This paper extends the work of to propose a web-based client-oriented anti-spoofing application that can be deployed globally.

Furthermore, unlike in, the application handles alert messages and spoofed emails more efficiently, preventing them from blocking up the user's inbox. Additionally, receivers can send explicit feedback notification messages to spoofed senders.

Existing:

- Legitimate mail header
- Time spoofed mail header
- DNS lookup
- Domain name checking
- Mail server matching

Future Enhancement:

- Finding IP ADDRESS
- Server name

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